

QUIZ**LAST NAME: WAZIRI****FIRST NAME: MUHAMMAD AWWAL****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show essential information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (Microsoft Word 365 on Windows 10)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. What are the rules to follow when joining two independent clauses?**
 - Comma followed by a conjunction, semicolon alone, or semicolon followed by a sentence modifier.¹**
 - Semicolon alone, comma, a comma followed by a conjunction.
 - Comma, a semicolon alone, a comma followed by a conjunction.
 - Semicolon followed by sentence modifier, comma, semicolon alone.

- 2. What is the order of the general rules of research writing?**
 - Find evidence, find an answer, draft a report, ask a question, revise the draft.
 - The draft report, find an answer, find evidence, ask a question, revise the draft.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*, 2nd ed. (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 17.

Ask a question, find an answer, find evidence, draft a report, revise the draft.²

Ask questions, find evidence, find answers, draft report, revise the draft.

3. **What are the primary sources of evidence in research?**

Diaries, letters, manuscripts, images, films, recordings.³

Articles, encyclopedias, books, dictionaries, journals, images.

Articles, diaries, images, films, books, manuscripts.

Letters, images, books, journals, diaries, articles.

4. **The research paradigms as knowledge claims are?**

Case study, ethnography, phenomenology, grounded theory.

Post-positivism, social constructivism, critical theory, pragmatism.⁴

Case study, post-positivism, critical theory, grounded theory.

Social constructivism, phenomenology, case study, grounded theory.

5. **Academic writing requires which of the following qualities?**

The right style, grammar, language mechanics, clarity.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 8th edition, Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 18.

³ Ibid.

⁴ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008), 8–9.

- Cohesiveness, clarity, language mechanics, boldness.
 - Grammar, language mechanics, clarity, error-proof.
 - Clarity, coherence, cohesiveness, boldness.**⁵
6. **The qualitative sampling techniques include which of the following?**
- Exploratory, homogenous, coding, snowball, random purposive.
 - Open-ended, exploratory, coding, sorting, synthesizing.
 - Criterion, coding, snowball, synthesizing, intensity.
 - Intensity, homogenous, criterion, snowball, random purposive.**⁶
7. **When do you use qualitative design in a study?**
- We are defining, expanding, collecting, summarizing, understanding.
 - We are exploring, explaining, describing, understanding, collecting.**⁷
 - We are exploring, defining, collecting, describing, expanding.
 - Understanding, describing, explaining, summarizing, exploring.
8. **When do you use “et al.” during formatting items in the reference list using the WHO style guide?**

⁵ Bloomberg and Volpe, 21.

⁶ Adu Philip, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study MP4* (Chicago: National Center for Academic & Dissertation Excellence, 2020), 20.

⁷ Adu Philip, 3.

- List all authors when there are three or fewer; when there are four or more, give only the first author's name and add "et al."**⁸
 - List some authors when there are four; when there are five or more, give only the first author's name and add "et al."
 - List five authors; when there are six or more, give only the first author's name and add "et al."
 - List six authors; when there are seven or more, give only the first author's name and add "et al."
9. **What are the appropriate order and styles of formatting a response paper in the home menu of MS Word?**
- RP Normal, RP Head 2, RP Head 3, RP Head 1, RP Quote, RP Title, RP Reference.
 - RP Title, RP Head 1, RP Head 2, RP Head 3, RP Quote, RP Normal, RP Reference.
 - RP Head 1, RP Head 2, RP Head 3, RP Normal, RP Quote, RP Reference, RP Title.**⁹
 - RP Head 1, RP Head 2, RP Head 3, RP Reference, RP Title, RP Normal, Reference, RP Title.
10. **How does the student evaluate the merit of study materials?**
- Organization, accuracy, completeness, overall importance.**¹⁰
 - Structure, language, syntax, grammar.

⁸ World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide* (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004), 7.

⁹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *How to Write a Response Paper* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020), 17.

¹⁰ Ibid.

- Style, accuracy, grammar, completeness.
- Importance, grammar, completeness, syntax.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publications, 2008.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 4*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Cleenerwerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *How to Write a Response Paper at EUCLID*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2020.

Philip, Adu. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study MP4*. Chicago: National Center for Academic & Dissertation Excellence, 2020.

Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 8th edition. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, and Joseph M. Williams. Chicago Guides to Writing, Editing, and Publishing. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. Geneva: World Health Organization, 2004.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.